

Developmental biology and host plant range of rice-feeding tiger moth *Cretonotus gangis* (L.)

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We studied the development of *C. gangis* on 20 common plant species from families Poaceae (14), Cyperaceae (5), and Commelinaceae (1). Unfed neonate larvae were placed on 25- to 30-day-old individual host plants in 20-cm-diameter clay pots enclosed in 10- × 72-cm cylindrical mylar cages with top and side vents of nylon mesh (1 mm²). Ten larvae were released per cage. Each cage served as a treatment, replicated 10 times, in a randomized complete block design in a percentage of larval survival, larval developmental period, larval growth index, and eggs laid by emerging females. Fecundity was determined on an individual basis for newly emerged moths, which were held in a 65- × 65- × 110-cm rectangular wooden cage frame with sides of nylon mesh (1 mm²). Honey solution (10%) was provided for food. A male was introduced for each caged female. 20 plant species, confirming the polyphagous nature of this insect.

C. gangis survived to pupation on all 20 plant species, confirming the polyphagous nature of this insect. Highest larval survival to pupation (n = 100) occurred on rice (79%), *Leptochloa chinensis* (73%), and *Eleusine indica* (72%). The quickest larval developmental period was on rice (22.1 d), although on all other plant hosts development was significantly delayed. These two developmental parameters resulted in a high growth index for rice (3.5) and *L. chinensis* (3.1), which were significantly higher than for the other plants. Rice (TN1) was the most suitable host (Table 1). All the plant species served as ovipositional hosts and supported complete development of *C. gangis*.

Greatest fecundity (no. eggs/female) occurred from moths reared on *Isachne globosa* (49.5), rice (46.7), *L. chinensis* (45.8), *Leersia hexandra* (44.7), *Cyperus kyllingia* (38.3), *Paspalum conjugatum* (36.7), *E. glabrescens* (36.21), and *E. colona* (34.1) (Table 1).

Life history data for *C. gangis* developing on rice appear in Table 2. Even though *C. gangis* is highly adapted to rice, it occurs rarely and has never been reported to be economically important.

Table 1. Host plant range of *Cretonotus gangis*, IRRI headhouse, Feb-Mar 1990.^a /

Plant	Parameter				Overall ranking ^f /
	Larval survival (%) ^{bc}	Larval developmental period (d) ^d /	Larval growth index (rating) ^e /	Eggs laid ranking (no./ female)	
Poaceae					
<i>Oryza sativa</i> TN1 variety	79.0 ±9.5 a	22.1 ±0.8 a	3.5 ±0.4 a	46.7 ±40.7 a	1
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i> (L.) Nees	73.0 ±20.0 ab	23.7 ±1.4 b	3.1 ±0.9 ab	45.8 ±12.5 a	2
Maize <i>Zea mays</i>	69.9 ±12.0 abc	29.4 ±0.9 c	2.8 ±0.5 bc	25.5 ±18.9 c-q	3
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	63.0 ±26.3 abc	30.2 ±1.6 d	2.4 ±1.0 cd	34.1 ±9.3 a-e	4
<i>E. glabrescens</i> Munro ex Hook f.	67.0 ±18.3 abc	30.6 ±0.9 e	2.5 ±0.7 bcd	36.2 ±7.3 a-d	5
<i>Eleusine indica</i> (L.) Gaertn.	72.0 ±18.7 ab	31.5 ±1.8 ef	2.8 ±0.7 bc	21.5 ±5.6 d-h	6
<i>Isachne globosa</i> L.	53.0 ±46.4 c	31.5 ±1.0 ef	2.0 ±1.8 de	49.5 ±38.9 a	7
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	57.0 ±22.1 bc	36.1 ±1.2 fg	1.7 ±0.7 ef	29.2 ±15.8 b-f	8
<i>P. conjugatum</i> Berg.	31.3 ±16.0 d	29.1 ±1.2 c	1.2 ±0.6 h	36.7 ±13.7 a-d	9
<i>Leersia hexandra</i> Sw.	24.1 ±23.2 de	31.5 ±1.2 ef	0.9 ±0.9 ghi	44.7 ±6.7 ab	12
<i>Brachiaria mutica</i> (Forsk.) Stapf.	15.0 ±7.1 def	37.7 ±0.9 gh	0.4 ±0.2 ij	17.7 ±7.1 e-h	13
<i>B. distachya</i> (L.) Stapf.	12.1 ±11.4 ef	38.1 ±1.4 gh	0.4 ±0.3 ij	16.2 ±12.5 fgh	14
<i>Chloris barbata</i> Sw.	10.0 ±0.0 ef	38.1 ±1.2 gh	0.2 ±0.0 j	17.8 ±1.7 e-h	15
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i> (L.) Beauv	8.0 ±4.2 ef	42.1 ±1.6 i	0.2 ±0.0 j	6.1 ±6.0 h	18
Cyperaceae					
<i>Cyperus kyllingia</i> Endl.	57.2 ±24.5 bc	32.0 ±1.6 f	1.7 ±0.8 ef	38.3 ±11.7 abc	10
<i>C. brevifolius</i> (Rottb.) Hassk.	52.1 ±24.4 c	38.1 ±1.2 gh	1.5 ±0.7 efq	15.9 ±4.6 fgh	11
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.)	19.0 ±8.8 def	35.6 ±0.7 fq	0.6 ±0.3 h-j	11.7 ±4.4 gh	13
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	22.0 ±9.2 def	43.0 ±0.7 i	0.6 ±0.2 h-j	33.2 ±11.9 a-e	16
<i>C. rotundus</i> L.	164.0 ±5.2 f	39.6 ±1.1 h	0.1 ±0.0 j	22.8 ±6.3 c-q	17
Commelinaceae					
<i>Commelina diffusa</i> Burm. f.	4.0 ±5.2 f	30.8 ±0.7 e	0.1 ±0.0 j	25.3 ±7.0 c-q	19
^a / Av of 10 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different ($P < 0.01$) by LSD statistical test.					
^b / Survival (%) = [Larvae becoming pupae/ Total larvae] x 100.					
^c / n = 100.					
^d / n = 10.					
^e / Growth index = [Larval survival (%) / Larval growth period (d)] .					
^f / 1 = best adapted, 19 = worst adapted					

Table 2. Life history of <i>C. gangis</i>. IRRI	
headhouse, Mar-Dec 1989. ^{a/}	
	x ± SD
Egg incubation period (d)	4.6 ± 0.8
Larval stadium (d)	
I	4.5 ± 0.5
II	4.9 ± 1.3
III	4.0 ± 0.7
IV	4.7 ± 0.8
V	4.0 ± 0.5
Prepupa (d)	2.0 ± 0
Pupa (d)	8.5 ± 0.5
Total developmental period (d)	37.2 ± 1.4
Moth longevity (d)	12.0 ± 1.5
Eggs laid (no./female)	46.7 ± 40.7
^{a/} n = 100, d = number of days	
SD = standard deviation	